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NEW CINEMA AND FILM SOCIETY MOVEMENT: CINEMA IN SEARCH OF AN AUDIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Film Society Movement in India and its trajectories, spanning from 1947 to 1980. The film society movement initiated and boasted by the prominent Bengali luminaries filmmakers', such as Chidananda Dasgupta, Satyajit Ray, Bangshi Chandragupta, Harishadhan Dasgupta, Ritwik Ghatak, Mrinal Sen, and later on, a gang of film school alumni, Mani Kaul, G. Aravindan, Kumar Shahani, Adoor Gopalakrishnan, Sayed Akhtar Mirza, Girish Kasaravalli, Nirod Mahapatra, Manmohan Mahapatra, Jahnu Barua, etc. were part of it, and alongside a substantial following of film enthusiasts that grew to approximately 100,000 members by 1980. While this movement primarily attracted individuals who regarded themselves as devoted film enthusiasts, it gained momentum through discussions reminiscent of those that animated left-leaning cultural movements originating in late colonial India, especially the Indian People Theatre Movement. It argued that a group of luminaries, those connected to this movement in some capacities, initially had their contributions marked by debates on the cultural and political roles of cinema. The main objectives of film societies were to forge a link between the cinema of the West and Indian art house cinema, as well as Indian audiences, filmmakers, and cinema technicians. After the independence in the second and third five-year plans, the Government of India took the initiative to strengthen the parallel film movement. Their agendas were not only to inspire young people to make but also to perpetuate Indian films in the international film market, where the primary motive would be to make 'Better films, for Better Audience and Better Society'. So, in this paper, I would like to explore how in the mid-1960s, notable shifts were found within the film societies that shifted the focus to aesthetics rather than a more pronounced political engagement with cinema. Simultaneously, it will also be explained that if it is factually accepted that the central government and other state agencies took affirmative initiatives in introducing and promoting Indian parallel films, why is it assumed that the parallel film movement only addressed the well-educated? If the latter is true, why is it so? Are narrative conventions in art cinema not accessible to those with less education?

In this proposal the question of cognition is important for the sake of cinematic narrative on one hand, on the other, for the emotive directionality – that directionality is indeterminate in nature in new wave Indian cinema. This research is not fully based on empirical research, nevertheless, I will take interviews of filmmakers, technicians, producers, art critics. Methodology adopted is qualitative in nature, based upon structured and in-depth interviews which enabled the respondents to opine regarding their understanding of the pedagogical and cognitive changes from Indian realism to Indian new wave. In this research we propose to use an inter-disciplinary framework where the sociological observations will receive priority because the content of parallel films and sociology are interlinked. Here the parallel new wave films between 1970's to 80's will be used as tools of understanding, criticizing and portraying social norms, values and institutions and as well as illustrating principles in the study of socio-political life.

Keywords: New Wave, Film Society Movement, Cinema, Audience, Politics

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INTRODUCTION

“When we came from film school, we were ambitious to make films in regional languages. Our seniors like Mani Kaul, Kumar Shahani, Adoor Gopalakrishnan, Girish Kasaravalli, and John Abraham initiated the making of different kinds of films that India can be proud of. They were not only a committed filmmaker, but they always inspired us in terms of educating and making aware Indian spectators of cinematic forms and language. When I was a film school student, Girish Kasaravalli, Mani Kaul and Adoor Gopalakrishnan used to come to take workshops, and they encouraged us to free our minds from the jargon of world cinema. They inspired us to reach out to ordinary people with our films. They were determined to educate the audience about new trends in Indian regional cinema and its technical and aesthetics implementation. Adoor was part of the Chitrlekha Film Society; Girish was a dedicated member of the Suchitra Film Society. Both are used to discuss the significant impact of world cinema, along with Indian alternative classics. Film Institute has always been famous for its regional diversity. I was from Assam, and Nirod and Manmohan Mahapatra were from Orrisa. Hariharan was from Chennai, Arun Khopkar was from Maharashtra, and Shaji Karun was from Tamil Nadu; we all were tenacious about making films in the regional language and making them available to ordinary people. Our alma mater, FTII, taught us the lesson of exploring the canvas of society and faithfully portraying its ethos to a broader audience through the film movement. FTII made us Dwija.” (Barua: 2023)ⁱ

In the mid-1960s, there was a noticeable shift within the film society movement from a primary focus on aesthetics to a more pronounced political engagement with regional cinema. This shift is entrenched because many film society activists in the 1960s criticized Satyajit Ray as an aesthete.ⁱⁱ During this later period, film society activists, especially film school graduates, engaged in debates about the role of political cinema in a postcolonial society like India. Some supported the idea of state-sponsored cinema, while others remained critical of its radical potential. However, they all shared the common belief that the radicalness of cinema should connect with the Indian people, a phrase that frequently appeared in their writings. This signified a growing emphasis on cinema to engage with the broader political and social landscape of India, marking a significant evolution within the film society movement.

Satyajit Ray, the Pioneer of the Film Society Movement and the Founder and President of the Federation of Film Societies of India, realized the problem perfectly. In his letter dated 31st October 1976, written to S M H Barney, Secretary to the Government of India, Ministry of Information & Broadcasting, Ray emphasized, “...I feel that Film Societies cannot function unless the government comes out in a big way to help them. The situation has become difficult, particularly due to the gradual stoppage of film lending by foreign embassies and consulates, which are the traditional sources of films for societies.” (Ray Satyajit: 1983)ⁱⁱⁱ They insisted upon Government intervention to solve the crisis. Accordingly, the Ministry of Information & Broadcasting, Government of India, set up a Working Group in May 1980, which observed that the Federation of Film Societies of India (FFSI) propagated Film consciousness among audiences. Within more than 30 years of the film society movement, only 200 film societies representing about 75,000 members, which the Federation of Film Societies of India recognized. A fair number of Film Societies are actively screening artistic films for their members, which are not affiliated with the FFSI. According to FFSI, about 300 applications are currently pending with the Federation seeking affiliation. This does not include many film clubs, which show only popular entertainment films to their members.^{iv}

The film is always treated as the most potent medium of communication. Identifying the influence of films over the masses, the first prime minister of India, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, drew a clear line. He was concerned about what would be presented; it must mould the public's taste, action, and reaction. Nehru appreciated the growth of the film industry over the three decades before 1955 and later. Nehru considered film as the medium to project the abstract of the government policy. He went a step further to emphasise the need to appreciate quality films as a precursor for making good films. In 1965, Chidananda Dasgupta, founder of the CFS, explained that 'without wishing away the difference between the art audience and the mass audience, it is still possible to direct film appreciation at two objectives: to inject more cinematic technique and attitude into the commercial cinema and to make it, raise its sights within reason: and to create the urge for and the climate, in which genuine good artistic expression becomes possible on a wider scale.' (Dasgupta: 1965)^v By 1964, all the Nehruvian ideas had crystallised: the National Film Archive of India (NFAI), the Film Finance Corporation (FFC), which later became the National Film Development Corporation (NFDC), and the Film Institute of India, which soon became the FTII. Cinema was being contextualised. The Indian government in New Delhi took an interest in cultural investment, including cinema. With that investment—adequate or inadequate—films such as *Bhuvan Shome* (1969) by Mrinal Sen, *Uski Roti* (1969) by Mani Kaul, and *Maya Darpan* (1972) by Kumar Shahani were made. The media dubbed it the Indian New Wave. The Nehru government tried to introduce the parallel cinema movement in India and introduced them to the world cinema market. The main motto of the NFAI, NFDC, FFC, etc, is to introduce the film as an art form. They were ready to explore the art and technology, with inputs of contemporary sensibilities of the West, where the medium originated.

In 1971, Suchitra's film Society was made with the initiatives of Narahari Rao and his friends Raghavendra Rao, G Venkataswamy, P V Rao, and Muddana. All of them were engineers, but they loved cinema greatly. It started as a forum where a bunch of selected movies from around the world would be screened in one of the theatres in Bangalore. In 1977, they conducted 'Nostalgia', a festival of films from the golden past. It showcased 70 films in 8 different languages. In that festival, Girish Kasaravalli's *Ghataradhya* received the best film award. '*Ghataradhya*' (1977) was one of the extraordinary films which received the Golden Lotus and national award within a year of filmmaking. Director Girish Kasaravalli depicted how a widow sets herself at a social disadvantage in a patriarchal society. In the '*Ghataradhya*' (1977), Kasaravalli's presentation is not only questioning the old traditional social and religious prejudices but also with its abstruse tradition, its superstition, and bigotry and its remarkable injustice imbues the issue with profound intensity.

Simultaneously, the director idolized the Yamuna in two specific ways, within entrenched social criticism: as a voice of oppressed Kannar Brahmin widow within social edicts, and simultaneously there also depicted as the feelings of femininity which consecrated as its heart, a thoroughly apolitical motherliness, which somehow seems to be evacuated of sexual desire, such idealisation testifies to the pervasiveness of a particular notion of gender difference.

Mr VP Sathe, a film journalist, was one of the founding members of Prabhat Chitra Mandal, which was part of the Maharashtra Film Society movement. Prabhat Chitra Mandal was inaugurated with the screening of Satyajit Ray's Chiriyakhana in July 1968. The film society was named after Prabhat Film Company to pursue the legacy of the biggest film company in Maharashtra, which V. Santharam and others started in the 1930s. The objectives of the Prabhat Chitra Mandal were to introduce world cinema to Marathi audiences. Though Marathi audiences regularly patronised the wealthy Marathi Theatre and enjoyed cinema, the world cinema was still not reaching them. We know that Maharashtra is the hub of early Indian cinema; pioneers Marathi cinema of Indian cinema, Dadasaheb Phalke, Kanjibhai Rathor, Damle, Phatelal, Baboorao Painter, and Santharam experimented with the content and techniques too. It was a common trend in Marathi cinema till the 1960s, and most were based on literature. With the influence of the film society movement, Marathi cinema between the 1970s and 1980s presents a formation co-existent with various competing industrial and artistic practices, encapsulated in a linguistically demarcated state with a prominent identification as a regional cinema in India. The proximity of the Marathi film industry to Hindi cinema in Bombay is a site of constant cultural negotiations between nationalist concerns and regional representations.

From the 1970s to the 1980s, Prabhat Chitra Mandal took the initiative to popularise alternative Marathi cinema. In 1972, Marathi/Hindi bilingual *Pinjra*, directed by V Santharam, introduced a milestone in the history of Marathi cinema. *Pinjra* was the remake of Stremberg's German film *Blue Angel*; this film was his homage to the German neo-expressionist influences. In 1977, Dr Jabbar Patel's *Jait re Jait* was one of the most remarkable films. It depicted the socio-economic crisis and rebels of Thakar tribes against the landlords and upper caste. In 1982, Amal Palekar's *Aakrit* and Shriram Lagu's *Zakol* were also significant productions. Since the late 1980s, there has been an increasing trend in Marathi cinema to include urban backdrops in their narratives. Films such as Mahesh Kothare's *Thartharhat*, *Danadan* and *Dhoomdhadaka* introduced crisp humour and appealed to urban and rural well. *Atmavishvas* by Sachin Pilgaonkar and *Kaalat –Nakalat* by Smita Talwalkar won several awards.

Filmmaker Adoor Gopalakrishnan mentioned in his interview that at the end of the 1960s, when the film society movement expanded and was led by film school graduates during the 1960s, one of its primary concerns was the need to redefine its objectives. Many commentators argued that film societies should not be viewed as art house cinemas. Arun Kaul emphasized the importance of conveying to the members that film society was not a space where people would just come and watch films without brainstorming. The purpose of the movement was to build up an enlightened, discriminating minority audience that should ultimately guide the so-called majority audience. These remarks underlined an inherent tension within the movement. On one hand, film societies were driven by a clear ambition to educate the masses about good cinema. On the other hand, the assumption that the average person needed to prepare to appreciate non-mainstream films raised questions about how and why such cinema could resonate with the general population. If mainstream Hindi, Bengali, or Tamil films captivated most Indian audiences with their allure of glamour and spectacle, non-mainstream cinema appeared too intellectual to attract the same viewers.

Filmmaker Manmohan Mahapatra mentioned in his interview that around the 1970s, New Wave filmmakers brought a technological transformation in cinema, which introduced radical changes in the film society movement in India. Film society was primarily confined to the urban, educated, elite middle class. Still, in the 1970s, when film school graduates were part of film societies, they aimed to reach out to cinema among the masses in the interior region of India. At that time, the technical possibilities and financial visibilities of the 16 mm projector facilitated films and reached out to the expected spectators in several remote areas in India. Nirod Mahapatra and Manmohan Mahapatra, two notable alums of film FTII, and a few cine enthusiasts from Orissa carried over the 16 mm projectors. They screened films like '*Bhuban Shome*' (1969), '*Bicycle Thieves*' (1948), '*Battleship Potemkin*' (1925), '*Do Bigha Zamin*' (1953), '*Pather Panchali*' (1955), '*Uski Roti*' (1969), etc. in the rural area of Orissa. It created collective cultural memories and material objects that engendered different aspects of film culture within the film society movement. This collective sense of enthusiasm is associated with technologies and instruments that enthralled and strengthened the objectives of film societies, namely that cinema needs its audience.

Renowned art critic Shamik Bandopadhyay mentioned that between the 1970s and 1980s, the film society movement was quite popular in the outskirts of Calcutta. Around 1972, cine clubs in Asansol and Naihati kept regular weekend film screening programmes. In politically disturbed regions like Imphal, two active film societies held film appreciation courses and hosted film screenings within strict military vigilance. In Kerala, eminent Malayalam filmmaker and film society pioneer G. Aravindan observed during the 1970s that 'the natural movement was not in the cities, it was in small towns and villages, which broke the intellectual hegemony of urban elitist groups. Around the 1970s, a film society in Heggodu, Karnataka, Ninasam Chitra Samaja took the initiative to organize a film festival in rural Karnataka. Almost a thousand people attended the screenings daily, though the festival was scheduled during harvest season, especially when farmers are over-occupied in agriculture. It was a splendid experience for the organisers because almost a large audience did not even know the films' language and the countries' names. Also, it was their first experience watching films on a large screen for a few of them. Twelve black and white films in 16 mm format, including some documentaries, were screened during the six-day film festival (19th to 24th December 1977). Films were '*Pather Panchali*' by Satyajit Ray, (1955), '*Bicycle Thieves*' by Vittorio de Sica, (1948), '*Wild Strawberries*' by Ingmar Bergman, (1957), '*Gold Rush*' by Charlie Chaplin, (1925), '*Battleship Potemkin*' by Sergei Eisenstein, (1925) '*Wages of Fear*' by Henri-Georges Clouzot, (1953), '*Rashomon*' by Akira Kurosawa, (1950), '*Happy Anniversary*' by Pierre Etaix, (1962), '*Nanook of the North*' by Robert Flaherty, (1922) and '*Satyajit Ray*' by B. D. Garga, (1963). The Ninasam Film Society's selection procedures were guided by their enthusiasm to expose the inexperienced audience to classics in world cinema and maintain a balance between 'emotionalism and 'cerebralism'. The Heggodu film festival exposed a disposition of urban, middle-class self-critique. As surveyed in the same report, 'with this experimental programme the pseudo-high-brow notion that laymen—especially the rustic, cannot evaluate films of artistic intelligence comes to an end.

The democratization of film societies also led to sharp differences of opinion regarding the works of specific directors. These debates were no longer theoretical or focused solely on foreign films; they now referenced the works of Indian directors. Much of the discourse rejected the earlier ideals of "good cinema" formulated by film society pioneers in the 1950s. The primary question under debate was whether good cinema could afford to remain detached from India's socio-political realities. It was contended that good cinema could not be considered as such if it divorced itself, either in form or content, from pressing issues like unemployment, illiteracy, poverty, violence, war, refugee crises, class disparities, and other social problems perceived as eroding the fabric of Indian society.

These debates over good cinema mirrored earlier discussions within organizations like the Progressive Writers Association, pitting "political" literature against literature driven by a taste for aesthetics, signifying the politicization of the film society movement.

FILM SOCIETIES AND THE AGE OF CRISIS

The main agenda of the Film Society movement was to promote regional parallel films and to create a platform which could forge between makers, artists, and audiences. At the beginning of the 1970s, a group of young filmmakers came to the forefront of the film society movement, and along with Hindi, in other languages, they initiated to portray their cinematic vision. Though it democratized the culture of spectatorship, it had a left-liberal orientation. From the 1960s itself, it was comprehended that Nehruvian's five-year plans were nothing but a utopia. Because it failed to deal with unemployment, price hikes, factory lockouts, food crises, and the political instabilities in India. From the end of the 1960s onwards, the Film Society Movement initiated a direct forge between the development of left politics and the propagation of film consciousness. Mriganka Shekhar Ray mentioned in the article 'Birth of A Film Culture' that when the new Indian cinema had given a unique shape to the film society movement, it mirrors shattered hopes on celluloid Filmmakers like Ritwik Ghatak, Mrinal Sen, Govinda Nihalani, Utpalendu Chakravarthy, John Abraham, they tried to portray the new turn in leftist politics and contribution of Naxalite activist in the contemporary socio-political milieu. Filmmaker Mrinal Sen shared in the interview that in Jadavpur University, a group of young Naxalite activists used to carry out films and projectors and used to go to the interior of Gopivallavpur, Devra, Sikkakulam, Midnapur, Purulia to screen the films like 'My Lenin' by Ghatak, or *An Indian Day* by S. Sukhdev, or 'Battleship Potemkin', 'Mother', 'October' etc. He mentioned that though it was a terrible time, a group of filmmakers and theatre activists like And Patwardhan, Goutam Ghosh, Utpalendu Chakravarthy, Utpal Dutta, Satya Banerjee, Bijan Bhattacharya, Hemanga Biswas, etc, were under strict surveillance under government police force. However, there were killings and murders around every corner of the city. Nonetheless, many students in urban India initiated a dialectical overview and class struggles in the film society movement.^{vi}

Simultaneously, its growth had been handicapped on account of the non-availability of a sufficient number of good films, the inadequacy of exhibition facilities and the lack of awareness on the part of the Government to appreciate the crucial role which this movement can play in creating audience taste through regular exposure of good films to a cross-section of the people. The Federation has organized itself in four zones without setting up an organization at every state level. This has prevented the Film Society Movement from obtaining financial help and support even from those state governments that are conscious of the need to encourage good cinema movement.^{vii} In this context, further through another letter dated 18th September 1986 written to Mr Rajiv Gandhi, the Prime Minister of India, Satyajit Ray emphasized, "... *To promote good cinema is an uphill task. It is more so in our country because of the huge commercial film industry. Today, Government agencies like the National Film Archive, Film TV Institute Directorate of Film Festivals, etc. are engaged in the same job. It was not so thirty years ago. The film society was Lonely Walkers. That the Federation and member Societies have done and are still doing a good job is evident from the fact that the Government of India entrusted the Federation with the responsibility of organizing the Documedia, the short and documentary film section of their International Film Festival held at Hyderabad in January this year. Despite this recognition and certain facilities like censorship exemption accorded by the Central Government, I very much doubt if the potentiality of this movement is fully realized by the government (emphasis by Ray). Otherwise, the film societies would not have been required to depend on foreign missions in India to supply films, even after thirty years.*

I request you to consider if an All-India movement like the film society movement can survive, let alone flourish, depending on foreign missions only. I am just mentioning this to underline the intensity of the problems which the film societies are facing now...". (Ray:1986)^{viii}

Unfortunately, Rajiv Gandhi was not motivated. On the contrary, it was under his patronage the Non-Resident Indians flooded the Indian film market with low-quality sex-centric films funded by them. Secondly, the electronic media captured the drawing rooms of the viewers. So, most members turned their back to the film societies, having found easy and cheaper alternatives. There was a quick decrease in the number of members. Some societies were even shut down.

On the other hand, from the early 80s, the leftist political movement suffered a setback. With the fall of the erstwhile Soviet Union, the distribution of films from the East European countries was massively disrupted and eventually stopped. An open market economy engulfed all attempts to resurgence international cultural and intellectual exchange. Money power dominated the production and distribution network of films. Since the film societies were not financially well-settled, large-scale degradation set in. Film societies were reduced to the status of being even smaller exhibitors. Then came a massive crisis in sound films. To break free from this dismal situation, the Federation started gathering and screening whatever films the Foreign Embassies offered. But even this attempt could not give the expected boost. The available films needed to be better, and even when good films were screened, viewers needed help to find them. The film societies should have shown interest in the Federation's other film-related activities. Thus, again, the loss was double-edged. On one hand, the Federation, by taking up the role of an exhibitor, rendered the societies more irresponsible and failed to connect them with diverse film-related activities. On the other hand, film societies moved ever further away from the movement. In addition, the Federation, a complicated seat of electoral politics, as an organization democratically voted to stay in power for two years only, could not take any revolutionary steps to ensure better participation in the movement. In this way, the whole subject became part of a vicious cycle. The Film Society Movement is not an isolated phenomenon. It is not an idea estranged from society. It is wrong to regard film societies as merely talking clubs that screen films, though sadly, this is the reality. So, finding an appropriate course of action poised to give this movement the right direction is essential.

Disturbed with all these happenings, Satyajit Ray again wrote a letter to Ajit Kumar Panja, Minister of Information & Broadcasting, Government of India, on 24th March 1987^{ix} he Government of India has taken the initiative to organize an international film festival every year. Nonetheless, its impact, for understandable reasons, always remains limited in scope. The enormous task of changing public taste and creating a sizeable audience for good films has long remained with film societies. This dependence (of the film societies on foreign missions for the supply of cinema) could have been more desirable and practical for the furtherance of the living movement. A comprehensive film policy was needed, which should also aim at the hitherto unattended area of film appreciation by the people at large. The proposed Chalachitra Academy was built suitably to meet the need. The tasks of the Academy had already been correctly spelt out by the Working Group. It was true that neither the government cared for setting up the 'Chalachitra Academy', nor did it form any 'comprehensive film policy' to spread the film culture, nor patronize the formation of any 'art theatre'. Even Ray's organization, the Federation of Film Societies of India (FFSI), failed to fulfil his dreams. FFSI began its journey in 1959 with only six film societies. The number of film societies affiliated with it increased to 24 in 1964, 111 in 1971, 216 in 1980, 253 in 2000 and then fell to only 230 or less in 2005.^x

Since its inception, the Central Office of FFSI has been situated in Calcutta, working on the same premises as the Office of the Eastern Region in the heart of the city and in the same building where the "Calcutta Film Society" is situated. Initially, the activities of FFSI were supervised simultaneously by Calcutta and Delhi. However, due to a subsequent increase in the number of film societies in different States, three Zones were created in the country's Eastern, Northern, and Western Regions, with their Headquarters in Calcutta, Delhi, and Mumbai, respectively. Initially, the film societies of the Southern part of the country were under the supervision of the West Zone. But during the 1970s, the activities of the film societies of the Southern Region increased so rapidly that a separate South Zone was created with its office in Madras in 1970. But after that, during the last three and a half decades, there has been no significant change in the structural pattern of FFSI.

It was observed that, from the beginning, there was some communication gap between the Film Industry and the Film Society Movement. In some cases, the industry leaders considered this movement their rival. This hatred was so farfetched that the profession of Andrei Brune, one of the founder members of the "London Film Society" was put in jeopardy. Andrei was a worker for Gainsborough Pictures. The management threatened to sack him if he did not sever all his ties with the "London Film Society". The reason behind this hostility is two-fold. Firstly, the film societies posed a challenge to the construction and subsequent marketing of the fantasy of the silver screen. Secondly, by producing one brilliant documentary after another, the film societies paved the way for showing what films were or could be. The growing popularity of these documentaries proved the success of parallel filmmaking. That is not the end. The film societies also gave rise to the conscious level of film literacy by collecting and exhibiting great films worldwide. This became another cause of threat for the dream merchants. The film journal 'Cinema' published by the "French Federation of Film Societies" gained immense popularity.

The much-acclaimed film magazine 'Sight & Sound' published by the "British Film Institute" depended mainly on seven hundred-plus members of the fellowship of films. 'Film Front', a low-key magazine published by "Film & Photo League of New York", was typed in ordinary quality and cyclostyled for circulation but significantly impacted the filmmakers during the decade of the 30s. The film magazine 'Sequence' of the 'Oxford Film Society' helped to develop a group of young, motivated filmmakers. Similar magazines like 'Film Comment' by "Lincon Centre, New York" and 'Film' by "The British Federation of Film Societies" contributed to the growth of a deeper understanding and appreciation of films. All these are the 'threat' to the dream-makers. But there are some exceptions, too. In 1964, 18 Craft Unions of the Bombay Film Industry of India came together to form a very active film society, "Film Forum," under the Chairmanship of K. A. Abbas. "Film Forum" spread the Film Society Movement south of Vindhyachal Hills of India.

The Film Society Movement suffered a setback due to the fall of the Soviet Union and the influx of the market economy. Though the European solidarity against the Hollywood monopoly helped the movement survive in France, Italy, Germany, Britain, Switzerland, Sweden, Spain, and some East European countries, the third-world countries are still lagging. Especially in India, the situation could be better due to so many factors. The vast commercial film industry is the central obstruction to propagating such a movement here in India. Moreover, there are obstacles to so many rules & regulations laid down by the Central & State Governments. Film Societies in most States are exempted from the entertainment taxes for screening foreign films. At the same time, it is mandatory to pay such taxes when presenting Indian films, even those of artistic value.

There are so many other examples. A need for more suitable theatres and films forces film societies to curb their programs. In the interview, director Shyam Benegal explained that "...the rapid expansion of disc market, easily available pirated VCDs & DVDs films stood as the main barrier to the film societies. Film societies can't show these pirated films to their members for obvious legal reasons. Any such activities are a highly punishable offence under several laws & regulations of the Government. Satyajit Ray's long-cherished desire for the effective government intervention to spread film culture by patronizing the Film Society Movement has not materialized." (Benegal:2018)^{xi}

On the contrary, through its different acts & laws, the Government is affecting the Movement in different ways. On the one hand, film societies need to get films from foreign embassies as before. On the other hand, they are not eligible to show even the original discs to their members for legal impediments. In contrast, there is no bar on such discs for home viewing. As a result, genuine film buffs are withdrawing from film societies and transforming themselves into home-viewers. Community film culture is being transformed into individual film culture. One can't exchange, interact, or share one's view with friends after the show ends. The target of the market economy is also to convert a person from a social element to an individual one. Therefore, community film culture is rapidly transforming into a particular film culture. Even at the industry level, the vast theatres are replaced by multiplexes. The market patronizes the individual entertainment process to such an extent that even intelligentsia ignore these subtle changes in social dynamics. Film Societies are the worst affected social groups in this process of transformation.^{xii}

Despite all these odds, some film societies like 'Ashay Film Society' of Pune, Maharashtra; 'Bardhaman Chalachitra Charcha Kendra' of West Bengal; 'Celluloid Chapter' of Jamshedpur, Jharkhand; 'Chalachitra' of Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala; 'Chandigarh Film Society' of Chandigarh; 'Chitralekha' of Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala; 'Cine Central Calcutta' of West Bengal; 'Delhi Malayalee Film Society' of New Delhi; 'Film Society of Jodhpur' of Rajasthan; 'Hyderabad Film Club' of Andhra Pradesh; 'Indo Cine Appreciation Forum - Chennai' of Tamil Nadu; 'Prabhat Chitra Mandal' of Mumbai, Maharashtra; 'Vijaywada Film Society' of Andhra Pradesh and a few others are running their activities up to a certain level of satisfaction. A few very active film societies, like 'The Baharampur Film Society' of West Bengal; The Karimnagar Film Society' of Andhra Pradesh, and 'The Suchitra Film Society' of Bangalore, Karnataka, have even built up their art theatres, fulfilling the dream of Satyajit Ray. But in a vast country like India, which is the highest film-producing country in the world, releasing about a thousand films every year in different languages and where the Film Society Movement has an age-old track record, such achievement is very insignificant. The spread of film societies in two tiny states - West Bengal and Kerala, where more than two-thirds of the total film societies of the country exist- proves that Leftist Politics had a solid influence on enriching the Film Society Movement.^{xiii} The failure of the Film Society Movement in States like Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, Assam, and some other states, where the traditional film industries are active, proves the fact that the film industry has very little to do with the development of film culture.

The mushroom growth of video halls in remote semi-urban and rural areas, regularly showing the trash of Hollywood, Bollywood, Tollywood, etc., and conveniently projecting soft & hardcore pornographies, is destroying the cultural taste of the masses very rapidly. The traditional folk arts practiced through the ages fail to attract people like in earlier days. Local performing art could only survive with the spontaneous patronization of the local commoners. The rapid growth of video culture smashed all these local art forms out of their roots. Moving images are entertainment now. The market economy considers it the most potent medium to conquer and hold the market share.

From a 15-second ad-teaser to a 150-minute commercial feature are all the weapons of the market economy. Each & every frame of the moving images conveys some message to the viewers to be decoded by them according to their cultural sense. Here lies the responsibility of the Film Society Movement to educate the people by developing their film sense in such a manner that they could read the text of moving images to decode the actual message and thus accept or reject the same. But ultimately, it did not work.

CONCLUSION

The Film Society Movement in India must still be aware of the hi-tech ICE-Age Phenomenon. Information, Communication, and Entertainment (ICE) are the three super-powers determining the cultural structure of today's society. From the air-cooled drawing room of the wealthy urban 'elite' viewer to the sweating hot rural video hall for the rural 'non-elite' commoners, moving images have their own language to communicate. Conventional education is absolutely an insignificant condition for the reception of this message. Instead, the ICE-Age denounces education, specifically the cine-education, to safeguard its interest. It 'educates' its target group according to its necessities. The Film Society Movement should concentrate its activities on this educational part. Conventional screening of some selected films to a small group of alienated urban elites will ultimately lead to nowhere. It should create a mass for the better cinema. It could only be done by taking good cinema to the grassroots level. The Film Society Movement should carve a niche in urban and rural pockets. It should encourage the audience to read the visuals carefully to evoke a healthy discussion at the end of every screening. It must target children and adolescents. Serious films with substantial themes always positively affect them and expose them to other cultures. Screening classics and independent cinema, especially documentaries and short films, at local schools, colleges, and cultural clubs could be practical in developing a film sense among the youth. A multi-media projection system could be a beneficial instrument to give satisfaction to the viewers in general. The women, the aged people, and the students will be attracted to and appreciate this venture. Thus, a parallel cine culture could be developed to fight the evils of corrosive trash. So far, the Film Society Movement has remained mainly as an urban phenomenon. Though the parallel filmmakers tried to promote the agonies and the picture of human suffering, the expected mass was kept away from the creations, and the educated left-liberal middle class only appreciated the similar film movement.

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ⁱ Jahnu Barua’s interview was taken by the author on 17th July 2023, Delhi

ⁱⁱ This criticism reflects the changing definition of "good cinema," which was now being redefined to encompass political engagement. A similar reevaluation of filmmakers like Mrinal Sen, Shyam Benegal, and Ritwik Ghatak can be seen in contemporary commentaries.

ⁱⁱⁱ Ray Satyajit (1983) ‘Our Films Their Films’, published by Hyperion, p-43

^{iv} Mazumder Premendra (2006) “Film Society Movement in India”, published by Chitralipi, Kolkata, p-20

^v Dasgupta Chidananda (1965) Film Society Movement in India (1965): A Survey, the article was published by Rao HN Narahari (2009), 'Film Society Movement in India', published by The Asian Film Foundation, Mumbai, p-43

^{vi} Mrinal Sen’s interview was taken by the author in 2017 november 22nd

^{vii} The traditional arts, as Smt. Kamaladevi Chattopadhyay has pointed ‘...are within the reach of most people since they are traditional. In fact, all the other forms are practised by the poorest people in the rural areas...’. This can never be the case with cinema in view of its sophisticated technological nature and the high investment, which

it involves. Furthermost, people to grow with some awareness of traditional art forms, which are imbibed at home and through schools and colleges. In India there is at present no such 'initiation' of the general audience in the art of cinema and thus people are left to cope with this power medium spontaneously leading to inadequate and distorted response. It is obvious that the Film Society Movement has a very important role to play 'initiating' audience in the appreciation of good cinema. It is in this context that we have suggested the Academy should be assigned the task of helping the growth of Film Society Movement. We further recommend that the local civic bodies should provide facilities by way of land at subsidized rates in the cultural complexes for setting up exhibition theatres exclusively earmarked for non-commercial exhibition of films by film societies. There is also need for the Film Society Movement to liberate itself from the constraints of commercial cinema houses. We recommend that the Central and State Governments should give grants to the film societies for purchasing mobile vans for exhibition of films. To begin with, the facilities for of these mobile vans can be given to regional organizations of film societies, which can utilize these vans for screening artistic films to the members of film societies on a regular basis. We also recommend that the Federation of Film Societies should set up organizations at the State level so that it can properly liaise with the State Governments for obtaining financial help and facilities for the film societies in the State...".

Mazumder Premendra (2006) "Film Society Movement in India", published by Chitralipi, Kolkata, p-20

^{viii} Ray Satyajit (1986), 'The Film Society Movement in India' published in the book 'Our Films Their Films' published by Hyperion, p-54

^{ix} Ray wrote that, "...The basic idea behind this suggestion for a film academy is to promote film culture in our country...A huge commercial industry which to say the least has not helped the public taste for good cinema to grow and develop since the advent of the film. The Working Group, therefore, rightly pointed out the need of Government intervention for affecting change in the situation for the growth of a healthy film culture...Very little has been done at the Government level to cause betterment in public taste by screening films or by other promotional activities.

Cherian VK (2017), India's Film Society Movement:the Journey and its Impact, published by Sage, New Delhi, -p-76

^x Mazumder Premendra (2006) "Film Society Movement in India", published by Chitralipi, Kolkata, p-33

^{xi} Shyam Benegal's interview was taken by the author on 28.12.2018

^{xii} Rao HN Narahari (2001), 'My Days With the Film Society', published by Sibina Service, Bangalore, p-109

^{xiii} Mazumder Premendra (2006) "Film Society Movement in India", published by Chitralipi, Kolkata, p-47